

EFFECTIVENESS OF SOFT SKILLS TEACHING MODEL ON ACHIEVEMENT OF STUDENTS

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Abstract

Soft skills play an important role in a successful career as well as during social interactions in the society. The scenario of higher education is changing very fast. Now a days only hard skills and experience are not sufficient for successful in the corporate world. This paper is based on effect of soft skills teaching model on achievement of students with reference to the employability skills. An experimental method was used for this study. A single grouped experimental designed was used to compare the effect of Soft Skills Teaching Model on the achievement of different aspects of soft skills among the Bachelor of Science students in Washim district affiliated by Sant Gadge Baba Amaravati University. The study reveals that, there is significant effect of Soft Skills Teaching Model on the achievement of different aspects of soft skills among the Boys and Girls and 68% principals responded that the present under graduate science curriculum is not related to employability skills.

Keywords: *Soft Skills Teaching Model*

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Introduction:

Skills generally refer to the ability of an individual to complete the assigned task or any particular task. It is also defined as the potential to execute a task with perfection. These skills enable individuals to accomplish the tasks, thereby improving one's competencies at their swift and pace. It is the ability to produce the determined results in the stipulated timeframe work. Broadly skills are divided into technical skills, personal skills, social skills, and life skills. Technical skills are those skills required to finish a job. Soft skills are considered fundamental for success in the present times, and such has become a much talked about subject today. It has come to dominate conversation across cultures and organization, just as much as it becomes a subject of interest even in day to day conversation. According to Gupta, Y. (2009) Soft skills

refer to personalities, attributes, qualities and personal behaviour of individuals. Soft skills include certain abilities such as communication, problem-solving, self-motivation, decision-making, and time management skills. Soft skills are often described as prerequisite personality traits such as leadership quality, integrity, optimism, communication skills, and social skills.

A few of the soft skills can be learned through training, but most of them come innately. Another significant difference is hard skills are mandatory for specific jobs. Soft skills are equally necessary for both life and career, although few job roles demand more of hard skills. Hard skills can be easily measured, and tangible and soft skills are demonstrated according to the arisen situations (Huma Hyder -2020).

Review of Related Research Studies:

The related reviews of previous studies are as follow:

Sharma Aditi (2013) undertaken a study on - Soft Skills as a Factor Influencing Employment in the Services with the objectives –a) To find out to the significance of Soft skills as a factor influencing the employment in the selected services and to create awareness for Soft skills development, b) To analyze the relevance of Soft skills in service sector as a concept' c) To assess what skills and competencies are required in the candidate for the selection in these service sector companies and also the skills required to retain in the job, and d) To find out significance of Soft skills in comparison to other influencing factors like academic score, experience, domain knowledge etc. Survey, personal interview, industry expert interview and telephonic interviews. The activities undertaken to develop Soft skills of the employees in the companies and the steps government is taking to develop it have also been analyzed. The findings of the study reveals that Soft skills has significant impact on both the growth as well as productivity of the employees working in service sector in selected services across hierarchy of management. Mehendale Anand Shridher (2014) undertaken- A Study of Implementation of Basic Employability Skills amongst Secondary School Students with reference to Pimpri-Chinchwad. The objectives of the study were- i) To study the attainment level of basic employability skills among secondary students; ii) To study the effect of socio-economic factors such as Gender, Area of Schools, Type of Schools and Medium of Schools on attainment level of basic employability skills; and iii) To study the role of school teachers to teach basic

employability skills. The study revealed that 1) some skills are difficult to learn at school. The social background is also important factors which develop these skills. Home environment, quality family life and parent's education are some major importance social factor which contributes the major role of acquired soft skills. 2) Secondary student s from the rural area score high level of attainments of writing, high order thinking skill and personal qualities and skill.3) Major student from the rural area are belonging to lower middle class and socially and economically backward area. Most of the parents are working in small scale industries. Azono Khatso (2018) undertaken a study on - Skills as a Contemporary Need in Education: An Interdisciplinary. Objectives were: To find out what makes the skills soft skills; to develop an integrated study of the philosophy of soft skills and emotional intelligence; To work towards a definition of soft skills; and To identify the possible alternate ways of teaching and learning soft skills. The study revealed that- Soft skills, needs to be introduced to learners and its values reinforced throughout their academic life to ensure their readiness to confidently meet life challenges. However, learners cannot be forced to be enmeshed in a web of socially and professionally accepted norms, to bow down and conform to the do "s and don "ts of a social and professional order. Rather than force it on students, a more gentle and effective way of making learners understand the significance of soft skills, will be to encouraged them to see it as a life skill, and in that sense as life giving; to learn it, not for its sake, but because of how it extends life itself or how it makes it makes life better.

Research Questions:

From the above brief reviews of related literature, following questions were raised for an empirical study of effectiveness of soft skills teaching model on achievement of students in different aspects of soft skills:

- Is the lack of awareness of the students about soft skills responsible for getting job?
- Can soft skills teaching model be made effective by special training programme?
- Can the soft skills of students be increased with the help of special training programme?
- What are the views of teachers towards effectiveness of soft skills teaching model?

An attempt was being made to study the effectiveness of soft skills teaching model on achievement of students in different aspects of soft skills.

Objectives of the Study

The study was undertaken with the following objectives in view:

- i. To review the science under graduates curriculum with reference to employability skills.
- ii. To develop Soft Skills Teaching Model for the students of second year Science Graduate Students.
- iii. To study the effect of Soft Skills Teaching Model on the achievement of different aspects of soft skills among the boys and girls.

Hypothesis of the Study:

Keeping in view the objectives of the study, the following hypothesis was formulated:

H₁: There is no significant effect of Soft Skills Teaching Model on the achievement of different aspects of soft skills among the boys.

H₂: There is no significant effect of Soft Skills Teaching Model on the achievement of different aspects of soft skills among the girls.

H₃: There is no significant effect of Soft Skills Teaching Model on the achievement of different aspects of soft skills among the boys and girls.

Methodology of the Study:

An experimental method was used for this study. A single grouped experimental designed was used to compare the effect of Soft Skills Teaching Model on the achievement of different aspects of soft skills among the Bachelor of Arts and Bachelor of Science students in Washim district affiliated by Sant Gadge Baba Amaravati University. In this study 56 boys and 56 girls of first year Bachelor of Science were selected randomly. A separate achievement test on different aspects of soft skills was developed to measure achievement of students in soft skills and an interview schedule was made for the head of the institution.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

The analysis of present data was done by using an inferential statistical techniques and percentage. The analysis and interpretation of effectiveness Soft Skills Teaching Model on the achievement of different aspects of soft skills among the boys and girls has been reasonably presented in the following tables.

Table 01 Mean difference in Pre and Post-test achievement of Boys in soft skills

Groups	Boys & Girls N	Mean M	Standard Deviation SD	Standard Error SE	Obtained t Value	Level of Significance <hr/> 0.01
Pre Test	56	10.05	3.071			
Post Test	56	18.25	2.337	0.488	16.80	Significant

Ref: The figures in the above table are based on the field data collected; If df = 110 then table t- value at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of significance are 1.97 and 2.58 respectively and r = 0.105.

From the above table, it is observed that the mean score in post-test obtained by boys in different aspects of soft skills (18.25) is higher than that of mean score obtained in pre-test (10.05). Further, it is revealed that the obtained t-value (16.80) is more than the table value at 0.01 level of significance indicates that the mean difference in this comparison is significant. Therefore, there exists statistically significant difference between the Pre and Post-test mean achievement scores of boys in different aspects of soft skills and hence the null hypothesis H_1 is rejected at 0.01 level of significance. Thus it showed that there is significant effect of Soft Skills Teaching Model on the achievement of different aspects of soft skills among the boys.

Table 02 Mean difference in Pre and Post-test achievement of Girls in soft skills

Groups	Boys & Girls N	Mean M	Standard Deviation SD	Standard Error SE	Obtained t Value	Level of Significance <hr/> 0.01
Pre Test	56	12.98	4.792			
Post Test	56	19.71	2.527	0.690	9.753	Significant

Ref: The figures in the above table are based on the field data collected; If df = 110 then table t- value at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of significance are 1.97 and 2.58 respectively and r = 0.109.

From the above table, it is observed that the mean score in post-test obtained by Girls in different aspects of soft skills (19.71) is higher than that of mean score obtained in pre-test (12.98). Further, it is revealed that the obtained t-value (9.753) is more than the table value at 0.01 level of significance indicates that the mean difference in this comparison is significant. Therefore, there exists statistically significant difference between the Pre and Post-test mean

achievement scores of Girls in different aspects of soft skills and hence the null hypothesis H₂ is rejected at 0.01 level of significance. Thus it showed that there is significant effect of Soft Skills Teaching Model on the achievement of different aspects of soft skills among the Girls.

Table 03 Mean difference in Pre and Post-test achievement of Boys and Girls in soft skills

Groups	Boys & Girls N	Mean M	Standard Deviation SD	Standard Error SE	Obtained t Value	Level of Significance 0.01
Pre Test	112	11.51	4.268			
Post Test	112	18.98	2.532	0.442	16.90	Significant

Ref: The figures in the above table are based on the field data collected; If df = 222 then table t- value at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of significance are 1.97 and 2.58 respectively and r = 0.1258.

From the above table, it is observed that the mean score in post-test obtained by Boys and Girls in different aspects of soft skills (18.98) is higher than that of mean score obtained in pre-test (11.51). Further, it is revealed that the obtained t-value (16.90) is more than the table value at 0.01 level of significance indicates that the mean difference in this comparison is significant. Therefore, there exists statistically significant difference between the Pre and Post-test mean achievement scores of Boys and Girls in different aspects of soft skills and hence the null hypothesis H₃ is rejected at 0.01 level of significance. Thus it showed that there is significant effect of Soft Skills Teaching Model on the achievement of different aspects of soft skills among the Boys and Girls.

Findings:

On the basis of analysis and interpretation of the field data and the analysis of interview scheduled of Principals; the following findings have been drawn:

- There is significant effect of Soft Skills Teaching Model on the achievement of different aspects of soft skills among the boys.
- There is significant effect of Soft Skills Teaching Model on the achievement of different aspects of soft skills among the Girls.

- There is significant effect of Soft Skills Teaching Model on the achievement of different aspects of soft skills among the Boys and Girls.
- 68% principals responded that the present under graduate science curriculum is not related to employability skills.
- Almost principals replied that their college provide special training on soft skill development to the students.

Conclusion: The findings of this study have shown that Soft Skills Teaching Model is most useful for achievement of different aspects of soft skills among the students. It is imperative therefore, that the under graduate curriculum should make provisions that ensure that these skills are cultivated in students which will be useful to them not only in improved academic achievement, but also in their future careers.

References:

- Gupta, Y. (2009). *Building a better business student. BizEd*, 9(6), 62-63.
- Garrett, Henry E. and Woodworth, R. S. (1981), *Statistics in Psychology and Education: Mrs. A. F. Shaikh for Lawyers, Pfeiffer & Simmons Ltd. Bombay.*
- Gulhane, G. Ale. (2013), *Research and Statistics, Anu Books, Meerut.*
- Hodges, D., & Burchell, N. (2003). *Business graduate competencies: Employers' views on importance and performance. Asia-Pacific Journal of Cooperative Education*, 4(2), 16-22.
- Huma Hyder (2020) *Soft Skills: A Research Study On Outdoing Academics And Conquer The World: The World PJAEE*, 17 (7)
- Rubin, R.S. (2009). *How relevant is the MBA? Assessing the alignment of required curricula and required managerial competencies. Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 8(2), 208–224.
- www.Shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in and www.Shodhgangotri.inflibnet.ac.in